

Moisture content was moderate among the different samples (see table). The percentage of ash was larger in rice hulls (17.2%), rice mill feed (15.9%), and rice bran (10.8%) than in other samples; it was lowest in polished rice (1.6%). All principal components were good sources of crude protein except rice hulls (3.4%), and all were low in crude

fat except for rice bran (15.1%). Crude fiber was greatest for rice hulls (34.7%) and rice mill feed (27.9%) and moderately low for rough rice (11.1%) and rice bran (8.7%). The different components had relatively high calorific values and were identical in inorganic element, calcium, and phosphorus contents. ■

Multiple submissions. Normally, only one report for a single experiment will be accepted. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submitting at different times multiple notes from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection will result in the rejection of all submissions on that research.

Pest resistance

Activity of the promoter of a rice lipid transfer protein gene in transgenic rice

E. Guiderdoni, N. M. Ferrière, Centre de coopération international de recherche agronomique pour le développement (CIRAD-CA), Biotrop-Gerdat Laboratory, BP5035,34032, Montpellier cedex, France; F. Vignols, Centre nationale de la recherche scientifique (CNRS), University of Perpignan, Laboratoire de physiologie et biologie moléculaire des plantes, URA565, 52 Avenue de Villeneuve, 66860 Perpignan Cédex, France; T. Legavre, H. Chair, and M.J. Cordero, CIRAD-CA; and M. Delseny, CNRS, University of Perpignan

Scientists have assumed that plant lipid transfer proteins (*Ltp*) participate in membrane biogenesis, which facilitates the movement of lipids between membranes. Expression analysis of these genes revealed complex patterns characterized by high cell and tissue specificity. Homologous or heterologous transfer of translational *Ltp* promoter-*gus* fusions in transgenic plants should facilitate localization of that expression. Recently, Kalla et al (1994) described aleurone cell-specific activity of the promoter of the barley *Ltp2* gene in transgenic rice. We report here activity of the promoter of a rice *Ltp* gene—a member of a small multigenic family—in transgenic rice.

A construct bearing a translational fusion between the promoter region of a rice lipid transfer protein (*Ltp*) gene (Vignols et al 1994), the *uidA* coding sequence, and the nos 3' terminator

(p Δ Gus1177) was transferred along with a plasmid consisting of the *bar* gene driven by the 35S promoter (p35SAc, Hoechst, Germany) to haploid, microspore callus cell suspension protoplasts in four separate experiments of PEG-mediated transformation, as described in Chair et al (1995).

Transient activity of the *Ltp* promoter quantified using the fluorimetric GUS assay 48 h after transformation was not significantly different from that of control protoplasts. However, protoplasts treated with the pEMUGN plasmid (Last et al 1991) exhibited very high GUS activity, suggesting that the *Ltp* promoter is not active in unorganized, undifferentiated cells.

The four experiments yielded 274 ammonium glufosinate-resistant calli that regenerated 136 plants. Histochemical assay of protoplast-derived colonies revealed faint GUS activity in some calli. Histochemical assay of 103 out of 136 regenerated plants enabled us to detect GUS activity in 47 plants, suggesting that the cotransformation efficiency reached at least 45%. The *Ltp* promoter appeared more active in the innermost developing leaves and variation in intensity of staining was noted among the plants. No GUS activity was found in the roots of plants exhibiting GUS-positive leaves. Southern blot analysis of 13 plants confirmed integration of both *uidA* and *bar* genes in the genome of regenerated plants (see figure).

Histological localization of GUS activity in transverse sections of shoots

of these plants permitted us to detect GUS activity in all cell types of the first innermost leaf, whereas that activity appeared localized in the outer epidermis and subepidermis of the second innermost leaf. In leaves of higher rank, activity became restricted to the outer epidermal cell layer. In fully mature leaves, GUS activity was mainly detected in stomate guard cells and in vascular bundles.

Southern blot analyses of 8 T₀ plants regenerated from protoplasts treated with the p Δ Gus1177 plasmid and exhibiting GUS activity in leaves. Genomic DNA was digested by *Bam*HI, which cuts the plasmid once, resolved in a 0.8% agarose gel, transferred to a nylon membrane, and then probed with an internal 1.8-kb fragment corresponding to the *gus* coding sequence. UT= DNA from an untransformed plant. The expected position of 5.9-kb fragments corresponding to tandem insertions of the plasmid is marked with an arrow.

Ongoing histochemical assay of reproductive organs of plants transformed with the pΔGus1177 plasmid permitted detection of GUS activity in the sterile lemmas and in the lemma and palea of the spikelets and in the maternal tissues of young developing anthers containing uninucleated microspores, but not in ovaries or in the walls of mature anthers containing binucleated pollen. We also found activity in pollen and in the pericarp of the mature seed.

Tissue specificity and developmental regulation of the rice *ltp* promoter make it a good candidate for driving genes conferring resistance to leaf-felder and blast that mainly develops on young leaves.

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Pest resistance—diseases

Sources of resistance to sheath blight

M. M. Reddy, T. Madhusudan, N. Kulkarni, and M. Kashikar, Rice Section, Agricultural Research Institute (ARI), Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

Sheath blight of rice, caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn, is becoming a major rice disease because of the increased use of nitrogen fertilizer and shorter, high-tillering cultivars, which together produce a microclimate that enhances disease incidence.

Because chemical control is costly and not effective, we screened breeding lines developed at ARI to identify resistant sources. This experiment was conducted with 166, 147, and 144 entries during the 1993, 1994, and 1995 wet

Table 1. Frequency distribution of sheath blight disease among entries. Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India. 1993-95.

Disease scale	Entries (no.)		
	1993	1994	1995
0	0	1	0
1	3	0	1
2	4	1	1
3	9	0	0
4	5	2	0
5	11	5	1
6	6	1	6
7	71	12	16
8	39	39	40
9	19	86	80

Table 2. Reaction to sheath blight disease of promising lines and other characters. Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India. 1993-95.

Line	Parentage	Disease score ^a			Mean	Plant height (cm)	Tillers hill ⁻¹ (no.)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
		1993	1994	1995				
RNR15336	Saleem/W12708	1.8	0.0	0.6	0.8	89	9.0	5.7
RNR82096	Tellahamsa/Akaswari	0.6	1.6	1.2	1.1	89	8.4	5.5
TN1 (check)		6.2	8.6	7.8	7.5	91	10.2	4.2

^a Mean of 10 hills.

seasons, respectively, under irrigated transplanted conditions. TN1 was the susceptible check. Each entry was grown in two 2-m rows at 15- × 15-cm spacing. Artificial inoculation was done at maximum tillering by placing 2-3 typha bits containing the inoculum in the middle of the hill just above the water level, tied with a rubber band. Ten hills were inoculated per entry.

To compute relative lesion height, the average vertical height of the upper most lesion and average plant height were measured at grain filling. Results revealed that most of the entries were highly susceptible (Table 1) but two entries, RNR15336 and RNR82096, produced low relative lesion height (Table 2) and appear to be resistant to sheath blight.

RNR15336 (120 d duration) and RNR82096 (140 d duration) have long slender grains and are being evaluated in advanced yield trials. ■

Effect of blast disease on rice yield

H. Surek and N. Beser, Thrace Agricultural Research Institute, P. O. Box 16, Edirne, Turkey

We studied the effect of blast disease on 12 rice varieties and lines at Edirne and Uzunköprü, Turkey, in 1995. Eighty kilometers separate the two sites.

The experiment was laid out at both sites in a randomized complete block design with four replications under continuous irrigation. Plot size was 20 m². Four hundred and fifty pre-germinated seeds m⁻² were broadcast in standing water on 20 May.

The same agronomic techniques were practiced at both sites. Fertilizer was applied at 150 kg N ha⁻¹ in three equal splits (basal dressing and top-dressing at tiller initiation and panicle initiation) and 80 kg P ha⁻¹ as a single basal dressing.